

Synthesis, Characterisation and Antimicrobial Studies on some Metal Complexes of 1-(*N,N*-Dicyclohexylamino)-methylthiourea

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The metal complexes of sulphur donor ligands have attracted considerable attention owing to their greater antibacterial and antifungal activities than those of the parent ligands. Substituted thioureas are known to possess a wide spectrum of biological properties¹. As a part of our systematic investigations on the transition metal complexes of some aminomethyl substituted ureas and thioureas, we have undertaken the synthesis, structural characterisation and antimicrobial studies on bivalent Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg complexes with 1-(*N,N*-dicyclohexylamino)methylthiourea (DCMT), (C₆H₁₁)₂-NCH₂NHCSNH₂.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of the complexes (Table 1) indicate 1 : 1, 1 : 2 or 2 : 1 metal : ligand stoichiometry. The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents except in DMF. The molar conductivities (10–45 Ω² mol⁻¹) of the complexes² in DMF suggest their non-ionic nature except for CoCl₂.2DCMT.2H₂O and CoBr₂.2DCMT which show 1 : 2 electrolytic nature both in DMF (143–148 Ω² mol⁻¹) and PhNO₂ (57–60 Ω² mol⁻¹).

The assignments of the ir bands of the thiourea moiety have been made on the basis of the data reported by Jensen and Nielsen³. In all the complexes, there is a lowering by ~40 cm⁻¹ of the band at 100 and of ~80 cm⁻¹ of the band at 1300–1270 cm⁻¹ indicating metal-sulphur bonding. This is in good agreement with most of the thiourea complexes already investigated⁴. The vibrational mode due to the (C–N–C) of the tertiary amino group of DCMT located at 1140–1110 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1120–1020 cm⁻¹ in the complexes on account of bonding of the tertiary nitrogen to the metal. In all the complexes, there is a slight increase in ν_{N–H} observed at 3260–3175 cm⁻¹ and in δ_{N–H} seen around 1600–1480 cm⁻¹. The bands appearing around 340–270 (M–S) and 470–400 cm⁻¹ (M–N) also suggest the chelating or bridging behaviour of DCMT through S and N atoms.

In the ir spectra of the nitrate complexes⁵, the bands of the coordinated NO₃ group are observed around 1520, 1275 and 1025–1000 cm⁻¹. For the perchlorate complexes, bands around 1280, 1130 and 1000 cm⁻¹ are observed⁶. In CuSO₄.2DCMT, the only sulphato complex studied, the

strong bands observed at 1175–1160, 1110, 1030 and 650 cm⁻¹ suggest the bridging bidentate nature of the SO₄ group⁷. In the aqua-complexes CoCl₂.2DCMT.2H₂O and CuBr₂.DCMT.H₂O, absorptions observed at 3530–3420, 1615 and 830 cm⁻¹ indicate the existence of coordinated water⁸ which is also supported by the thermoanalytical data.

In the electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes, the three well-resolved bands observed at ~8700, ~15270, and a ~24200 cm⁻¹ are attributed to ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{2g}(F), ν₁ ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(F) ν₂ and ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(F) ν₃ transitions respectively, under an octahedral environment around Ni^{II} ion⁹. Also the room temperature magnetic moment values² (~3.20 B.M.) obtained for the Ni^{II} complex are indicative of the distorted octahedral stereochemistry around Ni^{II}.

Among the Co^{II} complexes, CoBr₂.2DCMT which is blue-green in colour, exhibits bands at 7259 cm⁻¹ due to ⁴A₂→⁴T₁(F) ν₃ and at 15823 cm⁻¹ due to ⁴A₂→⁴T₁(P) ν₃ transitions for a tetrahedral environment around Co^{II} in the complex⁸. In the electronic spectra of the other Co^{II} complexes which are red-brown in colour, the two bands observed at ~16650 and 19570 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F) ν₂ and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(P) ν₃ transitions respectively, corresponding to an octahedral environment for Co^{II}. The absorption bands due to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F) ν₁ are calculated¹⁰ to appear at ~7770 cm⁻¹.

The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes show one broad band at ~12000 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to ²E_g→²T_{2g} transition characteristic of a tetragonally distorted octahedral stereochemistry¹¹ for Cu^{II} complexes. CuCl₂.2DCMT (green) has a room temperature magnetic moment value of 1.90 B.M. pointing to the monomeric octahedral geometry as well as the presence of one unpaired electron on Cu^{II} ion⁹. But for the other four Cu^{II} complexes (yellow-brown), the observed sub-normal magnetic moment¹⁴ values of ~1.10 B.M. at 300 K compared to the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M., could be attributed to the presence of strong anionic bridges between Cu^{II} ions in a dimeric structure and a partial quenching of the unpaired spins on the Cu^{II} ions.

The thermal decomposition studies (TG and DTA) on some of the metal-DCMT complexes

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have been carried out. The thermal stability order based on the initial decomposition temperatures is found to be $Hg^{II} \sim Cd^{II} > Zn^{II} \sim Ni^{II} > Co^{II} \sim Cu^{II}$. Mainly metal sulphates contaminated with traces of metal sulphides¹³ (at $\sim 600^\circ$) have been obtained as the final products of the thermal reactions. The abnormally high thermal stability as well as the unusual compositions, $2CdX_2 \cdot DCMT$ ($X=Cl, Br, I$) of the Cd^{II} complexes suggest a polymeric structure for them. The DTA patterns of the complexes studied have both endothermic features corresponding to $M-L$ bond fissions and exothermic peaks due to phase changes or oxidative decomposition of the sulphur donor ligand.

The antimicrobial screening for DCMT and some of its metal chloride ($ZnCl_2$, $NiCl_2$ and $CoCl_2$) complexes was carried out by the serial tube-dilution technique¹⁴. The percentages of inhibition of growth of *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* for different concentrations of compounds were found to be $\sim 71.6, 46.2$ and 27.3% respectively for 300, 200 and $100 \mu g ml^{-1}$ concentrations. It is known that compounds of sulphur are more antibacterial than those of nitrogen or oxygen compounds. Comparing the activity of DCMT complexes with that of the complexes of similar aminomethyl substituted thioureas, we find DCMT complexes to be lower in activity possibly due to the bulkier nature of the molecules. For the bulkier molecules it may not be easy to penetrate through the bacterial cell-wall and then to interfere in the cell multiplication process.

Experimental

DCMT was prepared based on Mannich and related reactions by interacting ice-cooled 37% aqueous formaldehyde (20.25 g) with thiourea (0.25 mol, 19.0 g) and dicyclohexylamine (0.25 mol, 45.25 g) in 1 : 1 : 1 mole ratio. The pale-yellowish white solid was recrystallised from ethanol-DMF mixture. m.p. $157-58^\circ$ (Found : C, 62.90 ; H, 10.54 ; S, 12.42. Calcd. : C, 62.45 ; H, 10.04 ; S, 11.90%). It was found sparingly soluble in water and ether, but fairly soluble in MeOH, EtOH and BuOH, and freely soluble in DMF. The metal complexes (Table 1) were prepared by mixing and refluxing the solutions of the metal salts and DCMT in appropriate mole ratios in suitable organic media (MeOH or BuOH). The solid complexes were washed with the hot organic solvent and dried under reduced pressure over fused $CaCl_2$.

The metal complexes were analysed¹⁶ for metal, halide and sulphur contents by standard methods. Conductance measurements were carried out on an Elico CM82T conductivity bridge using $\sim 10^{-3} M$ DMF solutions. The magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature by Gouy method. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer, far-ir spectra on a Polytech FIR-30 spectrophotometer, diffuse reflectance spectra ($MgCO_3$) on a Cary-2390 spectrophotometer and solution spectra (DMF) on a Jasco

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF DCMT COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % :			Mett B.M.
		Found/(Calcd)			
		Metal	Anion	Sulphur	
$ZnCl_2 \cdot L$	Colourless	17.00 (16.14)	17.85 (17.49)	8.05 (7.89)	—
$ZnBr_2 \cdot L$	Colourless	12.95 (13.23)	31.62 (32.34)	6.60 (6.47)	—
$2CdCl_2 \cdot L$	Pale yellow	36.18 (35.37)	22.46 (22.31)	5.14 (5.05)	—
$2CdBr_2 \cdot L$	Yellow	28.26 (27.64)	37.94 (39.29)	4.08 (3.93)	—
$2CdI_2 \cdot L$	Yellow	23.22 (22.45)	48.84 (50.69)	3.27 (3.20)	—
$HgCl_2 \cdot 2L$	Colourless	24.82 (24.77)	8.03 (8.76)	7.98 (7.91)	—
$HgI_2 \cdot 2L$	Pale yellow	21.35 (20.21)	24.14 (25.58)	6.54 (6.45)	—
$CoCl_2 \cdot 2L \cdot 2H_2O$	Reddish brown	7.85 (8.37)	10.38 (10.07)	9.19 (9.09)	5.10
$CoBr_2 \cdot 2L$	Bluish green	7.70 (7.79)	20.85 (21.14)	7.26 (7.08)	4.48
$Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot L$	Brown	12.68 (13.04)	— (27.44)	7.26 (7.08)	4.88
$Co(ClO_4)_2 \cdot L$	Brown	10.78 (11.19)	— (37.75)	6.23 (6.07)	5.30
$NiCl_2 \cdot 2L$	Pale green	9.36 (8.79)	10.88 (10.62)	9.68 (9.58)	3.35
$NiBr_2 \cdot 2L$	Pale green	8.56 (7.76)	21.95 (21.12)	8.57 (8.46)	3.06
$Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot L$	Pale green	13.62 (13.00)	— (27.45)	7.28 (7.08)	3.25
$Ni(ClO_4)_2 \cdot L$	Pale green	11.32 (11.15)	— (37.77)	6.20 (6.07)	3.25
$CuCl_2 \cdot 2L$	Green	8.86 (9.45)	10.82 (10.54)	9.73 (9.52)	1.90
$CuBr_2 \cdot L \cdot H_2O$	Yellowish green	12.50 (12.45)	31.61 (31.31)	6.31 (6.27)	0.95
$Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot L$	Brown	14.42 (13.92)	— (27.16)	7.12 (7.01)	1.12
$Cu(ClO_4)_2 \cdot L$	Brown	11.78 (11.98)	— (37.43)	6.13 (6.02)	1.07
$CuSO_4 \cdot 2L$	Light brown	8.94 (9.11)	— (13.76)	7.08 ^a (6.88)	1.10

*L=DCMT. ^aIncludes both inorganic ligand sulphur.

UVIDEC-430B spectrophotometer. TG and DTA data were recorded on a Stanton Red Croft 780 instrument with a working range of ambient to 1500° under static air. In the process of screening the antibacterial activity by serial tube dilution technique, the turbidities of the bacterial suspensions were measured on a Systronics 131 nepheloturbidity meter.

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NOTES

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